

Designing a management tool for a proposed postal code with modern standards based on a new division of the Libyan map to facilitate addressing in Libya

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ABSTRACT

Most correspondence or movement operations from one place to another unknown place require a postal code, whether for the source or destination, in order to ensure access easily, quickly and accurately. Most developed countries use a postal code in the delivery and access process, but there are some countries still uses the traditional postal addressing system, and the state of Libya is one of these examples, as it suffers from the lack of an accurate addressing system, despite the existence of a public postal institution, it uses a very old system called a postal box, symbolized by the symbol (P.O. Box), located within an institution, where the citizen does not actually benefit from it.

In an unsuccessful attempt, the Postal Corporation named the streets using small signs on the outskirts of the buildings, which residents do not pay any attention to, as they are accustomed to using alternative descriptions for their addresses that may be difficult to memorize and are considered impossible to include in mapping programs such as Google Maps and others that uses GPS navigation system, as these sites and applications are based in the postal addressing system on certain and fixed standards so that it is easy to infer those addresses through them. This has led to resorting to the use of private shipping companies, which usually have branches throughout the country to ensure the arrival of sent items in the event of shipping, and these are certainly not free services, not to mention the hardship in the case of wanting to move from one place to another unfamiliar place.

In this study, we will discuss the proposal to create a tool for generating and managing a postal code based on standards that will be extracted from the experiences of developed countries.

Keywords: Addressing, Postecode, Mapping System, Addressing Standards, Postal Code, Postal Address.

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INTRODUCTION

As humanity began to increase in population, and since it is human nature to move from one place to another, distances between people became more distant as the built environment became more complex. This caused the people in the past to invent several ways to identify the whereabouts of their relatives and friends, making it easier to deliver or reach them. Hence, the idea of using what is called a postal address or postal code came about. It is defined as a series of letters, numbers, or a combination of both, used as part of the address of a place or person to assist in the process of reaching or delivering things [1].

The postal code has several names, including Postal code or Post code, and it is used by most countries in the world, except for the United States and the Philippines, which use what is known as ZIP Code. Both perform the same function, but Zip Code is usually used to identify the location with increased delivery accuracy and consists only of numbers, while the Postal Code is usually used to track the delivery location and consists of a mixture of numbers, letters and symbols, which is a very precise difference [2]. The United Kingdom uses the term Postcode, while PIN-Code or PIN is used by India, CAP is used by Italy, CEP is used by Brazil, Eircode is used by Ireland, and PLZ is used by Germany. All of these names are synonymous with the basic term, which is Postal code [3].

The importance of the postal code lies in facilitating the process of reaching the target location very quickly and with accuracy, especially in emergency situations, as the accuracy and correctness of the address or postal code plays a fundamental role in many operations, whether commercial, personal, private, or even security. The postal code is also important in clarifying the geographical distribution of many areas with complete accuracy and clarity. In addition, the concept of address coding has become an original concept in search engine software (web maps) such as Google Maps, Bing Maps, and others [4].

Research Methodology

We will conduct a study of the most important components of the postal code used in some developed countries in the addressing process, in order to identify the most important criteria used and shared in constructing the postal code. We will then study the geographic division of Libya and the distribution of regions, proposing a new model for the addressing system based on geographic and regional divisions. We will then design a tool (a database management system) to generate and manage the proposed postal code based on criteria derived from the literature.

A Brief History of Postal Codes

Postal codes have evolved throughout history with the development of humanity, increased population growth, and the spread of distances. Each country has devised its own method of postal addressing, based on its size and geographical divisions. For example, the United Kingdom divided large cities into a number of regions and gave them what are known as "postal area numbers". London was divided into 10 regions in 1857, and Liverpool in 1864 [5]. By the time of World War I, most major European cities had area numbers.

This is also the case in most major cities in the United States, which have been issuing area codes since the 1920s. By 1930, the idea of expanding the distribution of area codes to include municipalities and rural areas began, and this idea was the beginning of the development of the ZIP code concept in the United States as we know it today. In 1932, the modern ZIP code system was introduced for the first time in the Ukrainian Soviet Socialist Republic, but it was

abolished in 1939[6]. Germany followed in 1949 , followed by Argentina in 1958, then the United States, which began implementing the modern ZIP code system in 1963 [8], followed by Switzerland in 1964, and then Britain, which introduced its current system in 1974, although it had actually begun implementing it since 1959 [7].

Components of a Postal Code

The structure and format of a postal code varies from one country to another. However, it is worth noting that there are three basic components that go into this structure: the numbers from "0" to "9," the basic Latin letters of the ISO alphabet, and spaces and hyphens [9]. Some countries use a mixture of numbers only, such as East Asian countries like Japan, Russia, and China, and some European countries like Turkey [10]. In addition to the United States, these numbers in the postal codes of the aforementioned countries refer to the numbers of provinces, sectors, units, and properties within regions and cities.

There are some countries that use a mixture of numbers and letters, and exclude some symbols or letters for their own reasons. For example, the Netherlands, where the following letters: (F, I, O, Q, U, Y) are considered reserved for technical reasons, but since almost all existing combinations are used, these letters have been allowed for new sites as of 2005, with excluding the use of the following letter combinations (SS, SD, SA) for historical reasons [11].

The Dutch postal code consists of 6 digits containing alphanumeric characters, divided into 4 numbers and 2 upper case letters separated by a space, such as: 1234 AB. Table No. (1) shows the function of each part:

Table 1. shows the function of each part of the Dutch postal code.

12	3	4	A space	A	B
Postal region	Locality	District		Delivery area	Subdivision of delivery area

The Canadian postal code system excludes the following symbols: (D, F, I, O, Q, U) because the OCR equipment used in automatic sorting, easily confuses them with other letters and numbers. The letters: (W, Z), they are used but not as the first letter, i.e. they are not included at the beginning of the postal code for technical reasons [12]. The Canadian postal code consists of a combination of letters and numbers separated into two parts by a space after the third letter. An example: K2G 1B2. Table No (2) shows the function of each part:

Table2. shows the function of each part of the Canadian postal code.

Forward Sortation Area FSA			space	Local Delivery Unit LDU		
K	2	G		1	B	2
Area code to which you are heading	Big cities' numbers	a specific area within the city	District number	Street address	Place number	
It refers to the East of Ontario	Except for the number "0" which indicates rural areas.	Part of the city, for example, the city center	If there are a number of residences	Whether main or sub	For example, a house, an institution or a piece land.	

The process of searching for a postal code in Canada is specific and regulated under the terms and conditions governed by Canadian laws. The search service is done through the website canadapost-postescanada.ca, which is specified by the government and has a mobile version available. It does not show you the full details of the address, but only shows you the destination. Also, the search process is allowed for a certain number of times for people who search for a postal code, and the search process is limited to personal services or limited internal commercial services [13].

The UK postcode, is an another example of a modern postcode model, which has been created and used by the Royal Mail as part of their address coding system. It is a combination of 5 to 7 characters (letters and numbers), that represent 4 levels of different geographical units. The UK postcode is a shortened form of address, which makes it easier to deliver items and reach a point (whether that point is private property such as a house, business, piece of land or a mailbox in a particular area).

Each postcode in the UK consists of two parts separated by a space. The first part is called the outward part of the code (outcode) and consists of two letters and a number, such as PO1. This part allows mail to be sent to the correct local area for delivery, as it contains data for the region and district to which the mail will be sent for delivery. The second part is called the inward part, and is used to sort mail at the local delivery office. It consists of a number and two letters, such as 3AX. The numeric part identifies the sector within the postal area, and then the alphabetical letters identify one or more private or public properties within the sector [14]. Table No. (3) shows the details of the contents of the British postcode:

Table3. shows the function of each part of the British postal code.

The Outward or outcode postcode			The Inward postcode		
P	O	1	3	A	X
These letters indicate the postal code of Portsmouth city.		This number indicates the postal code area within the Portsmouth region.	space	This number refers to a sector within the postal code area.	These letters indicate the unit's postal code, which identifies one or more delivery points, whether it is a separate property such as a house or institution, or a large property such as a large apartment building.

Extracting The Most Important Common Components Of A Postal Code

From the examples mentioned above, the most important components of a postal code, which make the address more accurate and comprehensive of most of the location's details, can be summarized in the following points:

- 1- The county code or number, if applicable.
- 2- The area or city code or number.
- 3- The sector code or number within the area.
- 4- The code or number of the delivery or arrival point, whether it is a private property, a residential building, or an institution.

The Geographical And Administrative Divisions Of The State Of Libya

Libya was divided in 1934 during the Italian colonial era into three provinces: Tripoli, Fezzan, and Cyrenaica, as shown in Figure (1), where the green color indicates the province of Tripoli, the red color indicates the province of Fezzan, and the black color indicates the province of Cyrenaica:

Fig 1: Shows The Division of Libya During the Italian Colonial Period into Three Provinces

This division continued after independence. During the rule of the Libyan Kingdom in 1963, Libya was re-divided into 10 main governorates, as shown in Table No. (4), in order:

Table 4. Shows the division of Libya into 10 governorates during the rule of the Libyan Kingdom in 1963.

1- Green Mountain Governorate	2- Derna Governorate	3- Benghazi Governorate	4- Ubari Governorate	5- Sabha Governorate
6- Misurata Governorate	7- Al-Khums Governorate	8- Western Mountain Governorate	9- Tripoli Governorate	10- Zawiya Governorate

After 1969, the Western Mountain Governorate was modified and renamed to Gharyan Governorate in 1970. Also, the Green Mountain Governorate was also renamed to Al Bayda Governorate in 1971. In 1983, this division was abolished and replaced by 46 municipalities. The number of these municipalities then decreased to 25 municipalities in 1987. Then, after 1995, the municipal division was abolished and replaced by what is locally known as the Shaabiyat, where the number of Shaabiyat at that time was 13 [1]. In 1998, the number of Shaabiyat increased to 26, and by 2001, the number increased to 32 Shaabiya, then was decreased to 22 in 2007, and Libya has remained on this division until the present time [15], as shown in Table No. (5):

Table 5. Shows the number of shaabiyat determined in 2007, which are 22 shaabiya.

1	Albotnan	6	Alwahat	11	Tripoli	16	Nalut	21	Ghat
2	Derna	7	Alkofra	12	Aljfara	17	Aljufra	22	Murzq
3	Green Mountain	8	Sirt	13	Zawiya	18	Wadi Alshti		
4	Almarj	9	Misurata	14	Zwara	19	Sabha		
5	Benghazi	10	Almirgb	15	Western Mountain	20	Wadi Alhaia		

It is worth noting that each region (Shaabiya) includes a number of cities or villages located within its area, and the map shown in Figure No. (2) shows the distribution of these regions “Shaabiyat” and their locations and scope throughout the Libyan territory according to the numbering sequence in Table No. (5) mentioned above:

Fig2: Shows The Distribution Of The 22 Shaabiya, According To The 2007 Division.

The Proposed New Division Of Libya's Map

Based on the experiences of countries using a modern postal coding system based on dividing maps into provinces, regions, and internal units, and based on Libya's geographic division, we think that combining Libya's division systems (the three-province system of 1934 and the 22-Shaabiya system of 2007) will give the proposed postal code greater comprehensiveness and precision in its composition.

In other words, the proposed new division of Libya's map will retain the three main provinces of the 1934 division (Cyrenaica, Tripolitania, and Fezzan), merging them with the 2007 division system, which contained 22 Shaabiya (formerly districts), so that each province would have a number of regions, as shown in Figure (3):

Fig3: shows the proposed new division of the map of Libya after merging the two division systems of 1934 and 2007.

According to figure No. (3), Cyrenaica province, which will be given the letter symbol (C), will include 7 regions, while Tripoli province, which will be given the symbol (T), will include 9 regions, and Fezzan province will be given the symbol (F) and will include 6 regions, as shown in Table No. (6) below:

Table 6. shows the proposed new division after merging the 1934 system with the 2007 system.

Cyrenaica Province represented by the symbol (C) and its affiliated regions:		Tripoli Province represented by the symbol (T) and its affiliated regions:				Fezzan Province represented by the symbol (F) and its affiliated regions:	
1	Albotnan	8	Sirt	15	Western Mountain	17	Aljufra
2	Derna	9	Misurata	16	Nalut	18	Alshti
3	Green Mountain	10	Almirgb			19	Sabha
4	Almarj	11	Tripoli			20	Alhaia
5	Benghazi	12	Aljfara			21	Ghat
6	Alwihat	13	Zawiya			22	Murzq
7	Alkofra	14	Zwara				

The proposed Libyan postal code format

The proposed Libyan postal code format and layout will be as shown in Figure (4), which will serve as an address that facilitates the process of moving and sending items. It will consist of two main parts, and the symbol (-) will be used to separate the sections of the postal address:

Fig4: shows the general form of the proposed postal code formula and an explanation of its most important sections.

1- The outer part: This part indicates the location of the postal code within one of the three main provinces (Tripoli, Cyrenaica, Fezzan). It consists of two sections:

- The first section: The province code, which consists of one of the alphabetical letters (C, T, or F), followed by the number of the region within the province, as shown in Table (6) above, and then the separator symbol (-).
- The second section: It contains the number of the city or village within the region referred to in the first section. It consists of one or more boxes according to the numbering sequence of cities and villages, followed by the symbol (-).

2- The inner part: This section indicates the delivery point within the city or village. It consists of an alphabetical letter indicating a specific sector within the city or village, followed by a number indicating the property (delivery point), whether it is a private home, residential building, institution, piece of land or a post office.

It is worth noting that the number (property, city or village and region) is not limited to a specific number of digits, meaning that the number may be one or more digits, and Table No. (7) explains the details of the contents of a proposed Libyan postal code in more detail:

Table7. shows the details of each section of the proposed postal code.

outer part of the postal address				Inner part of postal address		
It includes the province code and the areas within its scope, in addition to the cities and villages within these areas.				Delivery point within the city		
B	2	A separator symbol (-)	1	A separator symbol (-)	S	9
province code	Area number		City or village number within the region		Sector code within the city or village	Property number
It refers to the Cyrenaica province	Derna area as referred to in the zoning		Derna City		For example, the East Coast	For example, house number 9

It is recommended that the proposed postal code, to be assigned to the piece of land itself, on which the property is located. In other words, if the property is a house, residential building, institution or even a piece of land, the postal code indicates its location on the map, facilitating the delivery and arrival process. In addition, if the property contains several apartments, like a residential building, then the postal address will include the property's postal code followed by the apartment number.

Designing the tool to manage the proposed postal code

This tool was specifically designed to generate and manage the proposed postal code based on the criteria identified above. It is a database management system that will serve as the main database for all postal codes in Libya. It is currently being developed as a Windows application for testing purposes. Once officially approved by the relevant authorities, it will be developed into a website and mobile application.

The C# programming language has been used within Visual Studio environment due to its capabilities, power, ease, and flexibility. Additionally, a SQL database has also been designed to store all postal codes that have been generated by the tool. As shown in Figure (5), the application's main interface contains three main sections. The first section, on the right of the application screen, is dedicated to everything related to adding, deleting, and modifying postal codes, in addition to some interface controls, such as displaying certain labels, and the ability to generate QR for a specific postcode.

Fig5: The main interface of the proposed Libyan postal code management application.

The second section, located in the middle of the interface, displays the map of Libya, including its symbols, divisions, and regions. It also allows you to zoom in and out to add more details when clicking on a specific position, including the internal divisions of regions, cities and villages, and it is linked to the first and third sections. The third section is located to the left of the interface and provides some helpful tools, such as adding arrows and circles to define a specific sector or location. It also offers the ability to color a specific part of the map and add a hint to the specific

location. This makes it a helpful tool suitable for researchers and geographers and also those interested in mapping works, as shown in Figure (6).

Fig6: How to color an area, and add a circle and arrow to a specific place on the map for a specific purpose.

To add a new postal code to a place, simply zoom in on the map using the zoom tool, then click on the place you want to address with the postal code, where the coordinates of the place will be saved automatically. Then we choose the province code and enter the area number, followed by entering the city or village number, then we enter the internal sector (division) code and then a number for the property will be generated automatically, because the tool is able to remember the last postcode in that area, as shown in Figure No. (7).

Fig7: The process of adding a new postal code to a specific location on the map.

It's worth noting that the application will automatically assign a property number, as previously mentioned, without the need to enter it manually. This prevents duplication of the same property number for two different locations if the two properties are located in the same sector. It also maintains the overall sequence of properties and postal codes within the database.

In addition, the saving process will include adding the property owner's name as an optional process if the property is to be saved in the database. Users can modify the data for a stored postal code by first searching for it, then changing the required variables, then saving these changes, or permanently deleting the selected code.

An additional service provided by the tool is the ability to save the current scene as an image or save the current scene settings for later completion by clicking the buttons at the bottom of the map in the second section. Users can also reset the current scene by clicking on New Scene to start a new project.

Recommendations Before Implementing the Proposed Postal Code

The concept of addressing is generally uncommon in the Arab region, or perhaps incomplete at best in some countries. However, in Libya, it lacks many elements necessary for implementing a postal code system, which it is recommended to address, such as:

1. Establishing street names, as residents are accustomed to using alternative street names.
2. Organized building numbering, as the presence of informal settlements and unregulated construction makes it difficult to correctly number buildings.
3. In addition, poor urban planning in cities, which is not based on proper plans, is also evident, not to mention the complete deterioration of these elements in rural areas.
4. Lack of citizen awareness of the importance of using postal codes.

5. The state's neglect of the postal sector and its addressing system, through successive governments, is due to a complete lack of awareness and a lack of understanding of the importance of paying attention to such matters.

It's worth noting that Libya faces numerous challenges when implementing the addressing system, the most prominent of which are:

1. Removing slums
2. Opening sub streets
3. Fixing place names, where the names of public places are changed randomly, which undermines the credibility and accuracy of the addressing process.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that Libya lacks a postal system that meets modern requirements. From what was presented, the most important elements of a modern postal code were extracted, contributing to the formation of the proposed Libyan postal code. It also revealed that implementing a postal code in Libya requires overcoming several obstacles, perhaps the most prominent of which is disseminating the concept and importance of the postal code, as well as paying attention to proper urban planning.

In addition, after testing and experimentation, the tool that has been designed to generate and manage postal codes, proved effective based on the proposed postal code structure. This tool can be further developed in the event of actual implementation and when technical and geographical obstacles are encountered.

REFERENCE

- I. Postcode: Definition of postcode, in Merriam-Webster. 2025, Merriam-Webster.com.
- II. Surbhi, S. Difference Between Zip Code and Postal Code. 2019 [cited 2024 18/4]; Available from: <https://keydifferences.com/difference-between-zip-code-and-postal-code.html>.
- III. Graham, R., Global Sourcebook of Address Data Management, in A Guide to Address Formats and Data in 194 Countries. 2017, Routledge: London. p. 630.
- IV. Mohamed, E. 2021 – 1443 فما هي فوائد؟ .
- V. PAF. The History of UK Postcodes. [Online Newspaper] 2015 [cited 2024 30/03]; Available from: [https://www.poweredbypaf.com/the-history-of-uk-postcodes./](https://www.poweredbypaf.com/the-history-of-uk-postcodes/)
- VI. Kuzych, I., "The First Postal (ZIP) Code in the World". Ukrainian Philatelic and Numismatic Society, 2009. Vol. 70 No. 5.
- VII. "The history of the postcode". Deutsche Post 2011 [cited 2024 17/02]; Available from: http://www.deutschepost.de/dpag?tab=1&skin=hi&check=no&lang=de_EN&xmlFile=link1017517_1004711.
- VIII. Grubestic, T.H., Zip codes and spatial analysis: Problems and prospects. Socio-economic planning sciences, 2008. 42(2): p. 129-149.
- IX. Conrad, R., Designing postal codes for public use. Ergonomics, 1967. 10(2): p. 233-238.

- X. Turkish Postal Codes and the Post Office. Information about the postal system in Turkey, including sending and receiving letters, parcels and other mail, and how to find a Turkish postcode. 2020 [cited [cited 2024 10/03]; Available from: <https://www.angloinfo.com/how-to/turkey/housing/postal-system>.
- XI. Postal Codes and Addresses in the Netherlands. Posting a letter in the Netherlands? Find out how to make sure your letter is properly addressed. 2020 [cited 2024 13/03]; Available from: <https://www.angloinfo.com/how-to/netherlands/housing/postal-system>.
- XII. Addressing guidelines in Canada. 2022, [cited 2024 21/03] Available from: <https://www.canadapost-postescanada.ca/cpc/en/support/articles/addressing-guidelines/postal-codes.page>.
- XIII. Postal Code Targeting Terms and Conditions. Canada Post 2022 [cited 2024 21/04]; Available from: www.canadapost-postescanada.ca.
- XIV. Royal Mail UK Postcodes Explained. UK Postcodes, Address, Wards, Grids 2022 [cited 2024 21/04]; Master database containing every known deliverable address in the UK. Available from: https://www.postcodeaddressfile.co.uk/products/postcodes/postcodes_explained.htm.
- XV. مشروع اعادة هيكلية التقسيمات الادارية منبر من اجل الاصلاح والنهوض. 2011, المنارة بالروين, د.م. للاعلام.